

Interview with Neil Holdsworth, Head of Data and Information, ICES

Interviewee: Michael Svendsen og Asger Væring Larsen, 10/6 2022.

“The International Council for Exploration of the Sea (ICES) is an intergovernmental marine research organization that meets society's need for impartial documentation of the condition and sustainable use of our seas and oceans.

Our aim is to advance and share scientific understanding of marine ecosystems and the services they provide, and to use this knowledge to generate state-of-the-art advice to meet conservation, management and sustainability goals.

We are a network of almost 6000 scientists from over 700 marine institutes in our 20 member countries and beyond. Over 2,500 researchers participate in our activities annually.” (ICES webpage)

ICES was CoreTrustSeal certified in March 2021. The work took just over 1½ years, and included the collection of information listed in CTS' 2020-2022 requirements. After submitting the application and subsequent review, ICES' application was revised once, after which the certification went through.

ICES initially had two certifications that they could choose between: CoreTrustSeal and IODE¹, where CTS was chosen. The decision was based on a consideration that the IODE also functioned as a data supplier, and questions about impartiality issue could thus arise. ICES believed that they would receive a more qualified feed back from CTS.

The certification process came after ICES had worked for a number of years to improve data flow processes and thus the incoming data. The certification was initially experienced by the employees and affiliated institutions' researchers as a burden and something that could slow down their work. But the fact that the work of improvement took place within the framework of a certification gave more motivation to go into it.

The motivation for certification was partly to give ICES better credibility towards the parties they advise, but was also an occasion to work with the internal processes and improve them. ICES took the opportunity to look at more processes than data-related, looking at the entire organization. The work identified some shortcomings which they then had the opportunity to work on. Thus, the certification acted as a kind of catalyst for improvement. But it was also a very big job, which not least requires a cultural change with many external partners around the sharing of data and code.

Not all the required documentation was possible to provide to CTS. There were a number of internal descriptions of e.g. IT infrastructure and back-up that could not be disclosed for security reasons. This was also accepted by CTS.

ICES considers the process a success that is highly recommendable for others to go through. Both for reasons of showing the outside world that you comply with certain quality requirements, but also because the internal process is useful. ICES will, among other things, use the certification to enable applicants for EU project funds to show an accreditation to the recipient of data.

¹ <https://www.iode.org/>